

Prosiding Seminar Nasional
Adiwidya 9
Pascasarjana ITB

**“SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION
FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY IN
INDONESIA”**

Dilakukan secara daring, 23-24 Oktober 2021

PROSIDING ADIWIDYA 9

SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY IN INDONESIA

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The potency of Electricity Bill Saving and GHG Emission Reduction of A Middle-Class House in Indonesia by Using Solar-PV Rooftop and Smart Home System

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Abstract. Recent natural disasters are believed to have been linked with climate change. Extreme weather disasters, such as heatwaves and intense rainfall, are influenced by climate change, while hurricane disasters are linked to climate change with the evidence emerging. Human behavior on energy consumption is blamed for one of the leading causes of climate change and global warming. Shifting to renewable energy and a green lifestyle is one action that can save the earth from the worst catastrophes. On an individual scale, start using our Solar PV rooftop and install a smart home system are some choices that can take. Besides contributing to climate action, using the Solar PV rooftop and smart home system also give economic benefit for the owner. Current regulations in Indonesia allow PLN consumer to install a Solar PV rooftop and sell the excess electricity to the electricity grid, reducing the monthly electricity bill directly. Installing a smart home system makes the home appliance more efficient and can reduce the electricity bill as well. In this paper, the potency of electricity bill reduction of a middle-class house in Indonesia using a Solar PV rooftop and the smart home system is examined and analyzes whether the installation is economically attractive or not.

Keyword: *Solar PV rooftop, Smart Home System, Middle-class house, electricity bill saving, emission reduction*

1. Introduction

Recent natural disasters are believed to have been linked with climate change. Extreme weather disasters, such as heatwaves and intense rainfall, are influenced by climate change, while hurricane disasters are linked to climate change with the evidence emerging [1]. Human behavior on energy consumption is blamed for one of the leading causes of climate change and global warming. Shifting to renewable energy and a green lifestyle is one action that can save the earth from the worst catastrophes. [2]. A series of a plan already set to mitigate the climate change, one of them eliminate the use of fossil fuel and substitute them with renewable energy.

Indonesia's Government committed to cutting its greenhouse gas emission by 29% from the baseline before 2030, as stated in Nationally Determined Commitment to the Paris Agreement. The commitment toward a resilient future is also shown in Indonesia's National Energy General Plan, which is stated in Presidential Decree No 22 the Year 2017. In those documents, the Indonesian Government targeted to deploy renewable energy for 23% in the primary energy mix in 2025 [3]. One

of the strategies to spread renewable energy use from the Indonesian Government is the utilization of the Solar PV rooftop.

As of October 2020, there are 2566 PLN's (national electricity company) customers who installed Solar PV rooftops in their building with an aggregate capacity of around 18 MW [4]. There was a reasonably significant increase in a customer who installed Solar PV rooftops compared to early 2018 when there was no ministerial regulation related to Solar PV rooftops. By the end of 2018, the number of Solar PV rooftop customers was 609 users. On 15 November 2018, the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources released Ministerial Regulation number 49 of 2018 of Utilization of Rooftop Solar-Power Systems by Customers of PLN. In those regulations and its amendment, PLN customers must limit their Solar PV rooftops capacity to a maximum capacity of 100% of PLN connected power. The customer also can sell the excess energy produced by the Solar PV rooftop to PLN's grid, with condition PLN only pay for 65% of exported electricity. It means if the excess energy exported to PLN is 100 kWh, then PLN will only pay for 65 kWh, which will be calculated as a deduction from the customer's electricity bill for the following month [5].

The green action can be done for a residential customer by installing the solar PV rooftop and utilizing the smart home system. Installing a smart home system makes the home appliance more efficient and can reduce the electricity bill. The Smart Home system can be managed through the selection of efficient appliances, improvement in customers' knowledge of and experience with residential energy management, participation in demand-side management (DSM) programs, and the deployment of an energy management system (EMS) [6].

There are many studies regarding solar PV rooftop of the building, especially for Indonesia, such as [7], [8], and [9], but most of them did not study the potency of Smart Home System for the building as complimentary. In this paper, the potency of electricity bill reduction of a middle-class house in Indonesia using a Solar PV rooftop and the smart home system is examined and analyses whether the installation is economically attractive or not. This study examined three scenarios: the application of the Solar PV rooftop, the smart home system, and the application of solar PV rooftop and smart home system. The economic analysis is done by calculating the payback period, which is obtained by comparing the total cost for each scenario with each annual saving.

2. Solar PV rooftop and Smart Home System

Solar PV technology was already used as no-emission energy production several decades ago. There is much study regarding Solar PV technology, including the more efficient solar panel and more reliable Solar PV power plants. In MEMR Regulation number 49 of 2018, the Solar PV rooftop typical configuration is consists of several components such as solar panel, inverter, distribution panel, kWh export-import meter. The solar panel is the main component of the system which produces energy. The Grid Inverter converts the DC output from the solar panels into alternating AC current. Both components are equipped with a circuit breaker as protection. The Distribution Panel distributes electricity to the electrical appliances and exports excess electricity into the kWh export-import meter. The kWh export-import meter records the electricity consumed and/or transmitted to the PLN Electricity Grid. The construction and installation of the Solar PV rooftop connected to the grid require verification and approval from PLN. The process involves submitting application documents to PLN, which state the equipment specification and capacity of planned PV systems from the provider [10].

The smart home is defined as a home with programmable electronic controls and sensors that regulate house appliances, mainly in an electronic device that responds to interior climate conditions to conserve energy [11]. The key equipment of smart home systems is system master, which including a communication network, interactive terminal, and smart electrical equipment. Smart electrical equipment can be a smart socket, smart appliance, and home security. The smart socket can collect real-time accurate and sensitive load data of electricity consumption, then control operating time [12]. The smart appliance is a traditional home appliance such as a refrigerator, Air Conditioner (AC), and

lamp that can control its power consumption based on the occupation sensing and timer. This study designed the smart home system by implementing smart socket, smart AC, and smart LED lamp.

3. Object of study

This study is examined the potency of electricity bill saving and GHG emission reduction of a house that implementing the solar PV rooftop system and smart home system. In this study, the middle-class house is a PLN customer in tariff class of R1-TR 1300VA and located in Pamulang, South Tangerang. A family occupies the house with 3 people. The daily electricity consumption by the house is around 14 kWh. The electricity appliances that use in the house show in Table I, and the daily load curve is shown in Figure 3. The current electricity appliance is a standard home appliance, not implement any smart appliance. The daily load assumed the same every day for a month. In this study, the electricity tariff for R1-TR 1300VA is Rp 1444.7 / kWh.

Table 1. The electricity appliances that use in the house

Appliances	Amount	Power (W)	Average Duration of use (h)	Energy consumption (kWh)
Lamp	8	10	8	0.86
AC	1	450	8	3.60
Fan	2	46	24	1.75
TV	2	90	13	2.16
Refrigerator	1	60	24	1.50
Water Dispenser	1	250	24	0.88
Magic Jar	1	350	4	2.02
Water Pump	2	300	2.5	0.80
Washing Machine	1	220	1	0.22
Iron	1	350	1	0.35
Phone's charger	2	5	3	0.07
Laptop's charger	1	90	2	0.09

As located in South Tangerang, the house is supplied by PLN-Jamali's Grid. Based on the Directorate General of Electricity of MEMR, the latest emission factor of combined margin (CM) of PLN-Jamali's grid is 0.87 kg/kWh in 2019 [13].

4. Simulation and Calculation

In this study, the house is simulated to be installed with a Solar PV rooftop with a capacity of 1.2 kWp since the current regulation only allows the solar PV rooftop capacity is 100% of PLN connected power. The simulation is done by using the Helioscope application. Helioscope is a web-based application from Folsom Lab which can design a Solar PV rooftop system. It allows the user to choose the building, configure the array of solar panels, choose the solar panel and inverter model. The produced energy from simulation already considers the array's tilt and azimuth orientation, component losses, and weather conditions [14]. Figure 1 shows the Helioscope model of the house and the component and configuration used in the simulation. The tilt degree of a solar panel is 45° follow the roof's structure, and the azimuth direction of the solar panel is 40° from the north because it follows the house direction. Figure 4 shows the illustration of how the Solar PV rooftop will be installed.

The result of the simulation shows in Figure 2. The annual production is 975.6 kWh, or the average daily production is about 2.68 kWh. The performance ratio is only 54.1%. The losses because cell temperature is relatively high because the averaging operating cell temperature is 45.3°C while the ambient temperature is 27.6°C. The monthly production throughout the year is quite not much different. In this study, the daily production curve of solar PV rooftop refers to a day in March with

the daily production is close to the average daily production. Figure 3 shows the daily production curve of the solar PV rooftop and the daily load of the house.

Figure 1. Helioscope model of the house and the component and configuration

From Figure 3, we can see that the solar PV production is almost below the load along the day. Only at 10 am, the load is below the Solar PV production. That excess power will send to the PLN grid and can be a reduction in the electricity bill. The cost of Solar PV rooftop installation of this calculation is Rp 18,000,000 for a 1.2 kWp system is refer to as solarhub.id's calculator. From calculation found that the monthly saving is about Rp 112,895 and assumed there is a service cost of Rp 200,000 annually for the solar PV. The payback period of the application of solar PV rooftop for the house is 15.59 years.

Figure 2. Result of Helioscope simulation

In this study, the smart home system simulation is done by replacing the current AC with new smart AC, which can sense and control energy consumption, add a smart socket for controlling fan and charger usage, and replace the lamp with a smart lamp with motion sensor. The smart AC in this study is LG Dualcool thinQ with Watt Control-Smart Ionizer 0.5 PK. The smart socket that is applied is the Bardi Smart Portable Plug which can control the on-off of the socket from a smartphone. The number of smart sockets in this calculation is 5. All original lamp is replaced with Kris Led lamp with motion sensor. With several assumptions, the new daily load curve of the house is shown in Figure 3, and the total daily load is 11.68 kWh. The monthly saving from applying 3 types of smart home appliances is 70.32 kWh or reducing the monthly bill for Rp 101,591.30. The investment cost to buy the smart

appliance is assumed Rp 5,640,000 by using the price tag in the marketplace. The annual saving from the application of smart home appliances is Rp 1,019,095 by assuming there is an annual service cost for the AC of Rp 200,000. The payback period of application of smart home appliances is 5.53 years.

In the application and solar PV rooftop and smart home system scenario, the daily load curve refers to the house's daily load curve when using the smart home system. Figure 3 shows the daily load curve and the daily solar PV production curve for this scenario. It is shown that the solar PV production is below the load except at 10 am and 12 am. So, the excess power of solar PV at that time will sell to the PLN grid. From the calculation, the monthly saving after using the smart home system with utilizing solar PV rooftop is Rp 212,588.16 and the payback period is 10.99 years. The CO2 emission reduction in this scenario is 125.18 kgCo2/month.

Figure 3. the daily load curve before and after using the smart home system and the daily solar PV production curve for Solar PV rooftop

5. Conclusion and Discussion

From simulation and calculation, the potency of monthly saving if the house installing solar PV rooftop with capacity 1.2 kWp is Rp 112,895 or 18.57% from the original bill with a payback period for 15.59 years and the GHG emission reduction of 67.89 kg CO₂/month. If the house upgrades the home appliance to the smart home system, the potency of monthly saving is Rp 101,591 or 16.71% from the original bill with a payback period of 5.53 years and the GHG emission reduction of 57.67 kg CO₂/month. If the house combining installs the solar PV rooftop and smart home system, the monthly saving is Rp 212,588 or 37.97%, with a payback period of 10.99 years and the GHG emission reduction of 125.28 kg CO₂/month. Economically, the saving from its installed solar PV is not very interesting. The small saving happens because of the limitation of solar PV rooftop capacity and excess power prices. The new regulation regarding the Solar PV rooftop, which gives more benefit to the customer, is prepared by the ministry and ready to release soon, so the potency of bill saving is more attractive [15]. The application to install the smart home system is more reasonable to take immediately. Moreover, installing a solar PV rooftop gives more benefits than electricity bill saving and CO₂ emission reduction. By installing the solar PV rooftop, a house can be more independent from the PLN grid so that when the outage happens, the house can rely on the electricity need from the solar PV rooftop in the daytime.

Future work-study may analyze electricity bill saving of using solar PV rooftop and smart home system in a house which already installed. Future work also may study a more complex smart home system.

References

- [1] J. Anderson and C. Bausch, "Climate Change and Natural Disasters: Scientific evidence of a possible relation between recent natural disasters and climate change (IP/A/ENVI/FWC/2005-35)," no. January, p. 35, 2005.
- [2] Climate Transparency, "Brown to Green," 2019, [Online]. Available: <http://www.climate-transparency.org/g20-climate-performance/g20report2018>.
- [3] *Peraturan Pemerintah Republik Indonesia Nomor 79 Tahun 2014 Tentang Kebijakan Energi Nasional*. 2014.
- [4] Humas EBTKE, "Akselerasi Pengembangan PLTS Atap, Kejar Target Bauran EBT," *ebtke.esdm.go.id/*, 2020.
<https://ebtke.esdm.go.id/post/2020/11/20/2698/akselerasi.pengembangan.plts.atap.kejar.target.bauran.ebt?lang=en>.
- [5] S. Saleh, "Rooftop Solar Power Plant," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://sunenergy.id/blog/rooftop-solar-power-plant/>.
- [6] A. Saad Al-Sumaiti, M. H. Ahmed, and M. M. A. Salama, "Smart home activities: A literature review," *Electr. Power Components Syst.*, vol. 42, no. 3–4, pp. 294–305, 2014, doi: 10.1080/15325008.2013.832439.
- [7] E. Tarigan, "Simulasi Optimasi Kapasitas Plts Atap Untuk Rumah Tangga Di Surabaya," *Multitek Indones.*, vol. 14, no. July, pp. 13–22, 2020.
- [8] M. N. A. Romadhoni, E. Erlina, and S. Azzahra, "Perencanaan Pembangunan Sistem Pembangkit Listrik Tenaga Surya On Grid Pada Atap Gedung (Roof Top) Berkapasitas 10 kWp di Inspektorat Daerah Kota Samarinda," Institut Teknologi PLN, 2020.
- [9] I. G. B. W. Yogathama, I Wayan Arta Wijaya, and I. N. Budiastira, "Desain Pembangkit Listrik Tenaga Surya (Plts) Mengikuti Pola Atap Wantilan Desa Antosari Untuk Memenuhi Daya 3600 Watt," *SPEKTRUM*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 83–90, 2021.
- [10] D. Setyawati, "Analysis of perceptions towards the rooftop photovoltaic solar system policy in Indonesia," *Energy Policy*, vol. 144, no. April, p. 111569, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111569.
- [11] B. Davidovic and A. Labus, "A smart home system based on sensor technology," *Facta Univ. - Ser. Electron. Energ.*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 451–460, 2016, doi: 10.2298/fuee1603451d.
- [12] M. Li, W. Gu, W. Chen, Y. He, Y. Wu, and Y. Zhang, "Smart home : architecture, technologies and systems," *Procedia Comput. Sci.*, vol. 131, pp. 393–400, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2018.04.219.
- [13] Ditjen Ketenagalistrikan, "Faktor Emisi Grk Sistem Ketenagalistrikan Tahun 2019," 2019. [Online]. Available: https://gatrik.esdm.go.id/frontend/download_index/?kode_category=emisi_pl.
- [14] D. Rizkasari, W. Wilopo, and M. K. Ridwan, "Potensi Pemanfaatan Atap Gedung Untuk Plts Di Kantor Dinas Pekerjaan Umum, Perumahan Dan Energi Sumber Daya Mineral (Pup-Esdm) Provinsi Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta," *J. Appropriate Technol. Community Serv.*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 104–112, 2020, doi: 10.20885/jattec.vol1.iss2.art7.
- [15] E. BELLINI, "New rules to boost Indonesian net metered rooftop PV," *pv-magazine.com*, 2021. https://www.pv-magazine.com/2021/09/23/new-rules-to-boost-indonesian-net-metered-rooftop-pv/?utm_source=dlvr.it&utm_medium=twitter.

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